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Sampling & Sample-Provision Protocols for AdMas in complex Matrices

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Acronyms Listed in this Document	
BMS	Battery Management System
CNTs	Carbon Nanotubes
FLG	Few Layer Graphene
GLP	Good Laboratory Practice
GMP	Good Manufacturing Practices
GO	Graphene Oxide
GRM	Graphene Related Material
LA ICPMS	Laser ablation inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry
LNE	Laboratoire National de Métrologie et d'Essais
PLGA	Poly lactic-co-glycolic acid
PLCG	Poly lactic co glycolide
PSU	Polysulfone
SOP	Standard Operating Procedures
ToF-SIMS	Time-of-Flight Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry
UC	Use Case

Contents

1	Introduction	8
2	Results.....	8
2.1	UC: Medica Water Filters.....	8
2.2	UC2: Abrasion and Sample Collection Procedure for Epoxy-FLG Composites	9
2.3	UC3: Graphene related materials in consumer sprays	11
2.4	UC4: Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) in Polymer Foils for thermal Applications.....	13
2.5	UC5: Poly lactic-co-glycolic acid (PLGA) for inhalable antibiotics (Material Family: PLCG) 14	
3	Conclusions.....	16

Table of Figures

Figure 1: Samples provided by Medica to testing laboratories (LNE) to assess exposure through incineration a) pristine GO, b) polyurethane, c) PSU-GO fibres and d) empty cartridge. 9

Figure 2: Abrasion process of pure epoxy and epoxy-FLG composite. Step 1: Epoxy alone or epoxy-FLG (2%) composite is mixed, moulded and then cured. Step 2: The prepared plates are then abraded using a Taber abrader placed fume hood. The abraded particles pass through a metallic probe and accumulate in a polycarbonate filter (0.22 µm). Step 3: The abraded particles from the filters are taken off by gentle scraping using a sterile spatula and collected in a sterile falcon tube. 9

Figure 3: Fabrication of Epoxy-FLG composite plates. Epoxy alone or epoxy-FLG composite are mixed with hardener (Baxxodur EC 301), moulded and then cured in the oven at indicated temperature cycles. The plates obtained after curing were used for abrasion. 10

Figure 4: Abrasion and collection of abraded particles. Epoxy or Epoxy-FLG plates are abraded at indicated conditions using a Taber abrader. The abraded particles are accumulated on a polycarbonate filter. The abraded particles from the filters are taken off using a scraper and collected in a falcon tube. 10

Figure 5: Steps to be performed on the cans prior to cell culture testing (see text above). a) Silicon-only and b) silicon and graphene samples. Third picture represents sample on test vial prior to cell exposure. 11

Figure 6: Steps to be performed on the mineral oil samples prior to cell culture testing (see text above). a) commercial product and b) sample on a test vial prior to cell exposure..... 12

Figure 7: Steps to be performed on the graphene plus mineral oil samples prior to cell culture testing. Third picture represents samples on a test vial prior to cell exposure, black layer indicates presence of graphene (see text above)..... 12

Figure 8: Steps to be performed on the graphene (100%) sprays prior to cell culture testing. Third picture represents sample on a test vial prior to cell exposure, black dots indicate presence of graphene (see text above). 13

Figure 9: CNT filled PU foils as a roll good on release paper. 13

Figure 10: Milling was performed in an ultra-centrifugal mill. In a first step (a) a 2 mm sieve was used for milling with 10,000 rpm for 1 min. In a second step (b) a 1 mm sieve was used for milling with 10,000 rpm for 1 min. The samples (c) were collected afterwards..... 14

Figure 11: Process leading to sampling of MyBiotech particles. 15

Figure 12: Samples to be shipped for further assessment are enumerated in Table 2. 15

Table of Tables

Table 1: Graphene-based commercial samples selected for testing in Macrame. 11

Table 2: Samples already shipped to MACRAME partners for further characterisation. The first four items are shown in Figure 12..... 16

Executive Summary

This report defines the sampling collection protocols performed at the Use-Case (UCs) sites prior to sending the samples to MACRAMÉ laboratories for testing. The Use-Cases include all five market-relevant industrial Advanced Materials (AdMas) in their complex matrices, where inhalation exposure or environmental exposure have been identified along the life cycle, or where there is a need for testing protocols for AdMas.

Since MACRAMÉ deals with transformed AdMas (i.e. those in relevant complex matrices, not pristine materials), the work presented in this report focuses on the development and adaptations of protocols relevant for sample collection prior to be delivered for characterisation and further analysis. Identified challenges include the size of samples that need to be taken, and nature of samples, which may prevent exposure assessment in liquid media.

The MACRAMÉ Use-Cases are as follows:

- Use-Case 1: Graphene oxide (GO) flakes in drinking-water filters (Material Family: GRM);
- Use-Case 2: Few-layer graphene (FLG) in battery management systems (BMS) (Material Family: GRM);
- Use-Case 3: Graphene-related materials (GRM) in bicycles/car lubricant consumer sprays (Material Family: GRM);
- Use-Case 4: Carbon nanotubes (i.e. CNTs) in car-seats (Material Family: carbon fibres); and
- Use-Case 5: Poly lactic-co-glycolic acid (PLGA) for inhalable antibiotics (Material Family: PLCG).

1 Introduction

Sampling protocols are important to allow for adequate standardisation and harmonisation. They guide the collecting of all necessary samples of a kind in a similar fashion and thus allow for comparison of experimental results. In particular, developing sampling protocols also enables to provide samples that are fit for the respective experimental conditions, e.g. free of contamination, which is needed for *in vitro* toxicological experiments. Furthermore, standard practices can contribute to avoiding risks to human or the environment while performing sampling, e.g. in case of sampling powders.

The five different MACRAMÉ Use-Cases (UCs) cover different material classes, different industrial sectors, different scales of production processes and, therefore, different sampling procedures and protocols are inevitable. In addition, the characterisation and subsequent experiments planned for the samples are different and, hence, the sample preparation including amount and pre-treatment, can vary.

2 Results

In the following paragraphs, the different UCs are introduced briefly, and the sampling procedures are described in detail.

2.1 UC1: Medica Water Filters

UC1 deals with water filters made from polysulfone (PSU) and graphene oxide (5% w/w). Previous studies showed that upon usage, no graphene is released or detected at 50 ppb (limit of detection) hence MACRAMÉ focuses on the expected end-of-life of the filters, which currently is represented by incineration. The following samples were already collected and sent to LNE for further assessment (Figure 1):

- -Pristine GO in powder directly from the manufacturer's (LayerOne)
- -Polyurethane in solid form as potting material (from isocyanilate and polyol)
- -PSU-GO fibre (as produced)
- -Empty cartridge (in a piece, as produced)

This UC did not require the development of sampling protocols since the commercial graphene oxide was aliquoted following standard practices (e.g. weighing was performed inside a plastic container using a stainless-steel spatula) and other samples represent solid material which did not require special temperature conditions or handling due to exposure to dust or harmful substances prior to packaging. Sterility of samples will be addressed after incineration at the testing laboratories prior to exposure to cell culture systems.

Figure 1: Samples provided by Medica to testing laboratories (LNE) to assess exposure through incineration a) pristine GO, b) polyurethane, c) PSU-GO fibres and d) empty cartridge.

2.2 UC2: Abrasion and Sample Collection Procedure for Epoxy-FLG Composites

The scope of this UC is to collect abraded material from the Epoxy-FLG composites for further toxicology experiments, which include inhalation and ecotoxicity assessment. Abrasion was performed by Empa (Prof. Peter Wick`s Group) on both pure Epoxy and Epoxy-FLG materials and samples were collected as depicted in Figure 2. For security reasons and to ensure individual safety and the sterility of the produced material, the whole process (steps 1- 3) was performed under a fume hood with airflow on. The instrument operation and sample handling/collection are only done after wearing protective gloves and FFP3 face mask.

Step 1. Fabrication of Epoxy or FLG-Epoxy Plates:

Carbon Waters provided the mixture of FLG (1%) and Epoxy (Epikote 827) composite. At Empa, Epoxy only or Epoxy-FLG composite are supplemented with hardener (Baxxodur EC 301) (ratio: 100: 33.52) and mixed thoroughly using a high shear mixture as shown in Figure 3. After mixing, the materials are casted into moulds to make plates (Dimensions: 23 x 21 x 0.4 cm) and then transferred into the oven for curing. The curing is performed in two cycles: one at 80°C for 12 h, followed by 120°C for 4 h.

Figure 2: Abrasion process of pure epoxy and epoxy-FLG composite. Step 1: Epoxy alone or epoxy-FLG (2%) composite is mixed, moulded and then cured. Step 2: The prepared plates are then abraded using a Taber abrader placed fume hood. The abraded particles pass through a metallic probe and accumulate in a polycarbonate filter (0.22 µm). Step 3: The abraded particles from the filters are taken off by gentle scraping using a sterile spatula and collected in a sterile falcon tube.

Figure 3: Fabrication of Epoxy-FLG composite plates. Epoxy alone or epoxy-FLG composite are mixed with hardener (Baxxodur EC 301), moulded and then cured in the oven at indicated temperature cycles. The plates obtained after curing were used for abrasion.

Step 2 and Step 3: Abrasion and Material Collection: The Epoxy or Epoxy FLG plate is fitted into a plate holder in Taber Abrader (Figure 3) and then abrasion is performed at the speed of 60 cycles/minute and a flow rate of 10.5 L/min. During abrasion, the abraded material passes through a suction tube and is deposited on a polycarbonate filter paper (pore size: 0.22 μm). After every 5000 cycles, the filter paper is taken out and the material is collected in a tube by gentle scrapping using a sterile spatula (Figure 4).

Speed: 60 cycles/min; Total cycles/run: 5000; Time/run = 84 min; Pump flow rate : 10.5 L/min

Figure 4: Abrasion and collection of abraded particles. Epoxy or Epoxy-FLG plates are abraded at indicated conditions using a Taber abrader. The abraded particles are accumulated on a polycarbonate filter. The abraded particles from the filters are taken off using a scraper and collected in a falcon tube.

2.3 UC3: Graphene related materials in consumer sprays

This case study deals with a selection of five commercially available Graphene-based lubricant sprays as shown in Table 1. MACRAMÉ will evaluate the toxicity of such products during the use phase of the life cycle using relevant cell culture models representing the human lung exposed to inhaled substances and particles and the aquatic environment (discarded product). Sterility of samples has not been specifically addressed, however it is likely that the content of the cans contains preservatives to avoid bacterial contamination.

Table 1: Graphene-based commercial samples selected for testing in Macrame.

Label GAIKER	Commercial name	Composition
Macrame – Silicone	Spray abrillantador acabado brillo	Pure silicone
Macrame – Graphene + Silicone	Spray lubricante silicona	Graphene in silicone matrix
Macrame – Mineral oil	Liquido freno mineral	Mineral oil
Macrame – Graphene + oil	Graphen oil aceite + grafeno	Graphene in mineral oil matrix
Macrame – Graphene 100%	Spray catalizador grafeno	Graphene in isopropanol
Label GAIKER	Commercial name	Composition

Protocol for collecting samples from silicon cans: Based on Figure 5 (a and b) lift up the attached tube and bring the tube close to a sterile glass vial (1, 2), then press the trigger lever to activate the pump. Once this is achieved fill the sterile vial with a sufficient volume of the product (3) and pipette the product from the glass vial to prepare the testing concentrations.

(a) Silicon samples

(b) Silicon-based samples

Figure 5: Steps to be performed on the cans prior to cell culture testing (see text above). a) Silicon-only and b) silicon and graphene samples. Third picture represents sample on test vial prior to cell exposure.

(a)

(b)

Protocol for collecting samples from mineral oil tubes: As shown in Figure 6, unscrew the lid to open the tube and bring the flask close to a sterile glass vial, squeeze the tube to extract the product, fill the sterile vial with a sufficient volume of the product and finally pipette the product from the glass vial to prepare the testing concentrations.

Figure 6: Steps to be performed on the mineral oil samples prior to cell culture testing (see text above). a) commercial product and b) sample on a test vial prior to cell exposure.

Protocol for collecting samples from graphene plus mineral oil cans: Following Figure 7, lift up the attached tube and bring the tube close to a sterile glass vial (1, 2), press the trigger lever to activate the pump, then fill the sterile vial with a sufficient volume of the product (3), and finally pipette the product from the glass vial to prepare the testing concentrations.

Figure 7: Steps to be performed on the graphene plus mineral oil samples prior to cell culture testing. Third picture represents samples on a test vial prior to cell exposure, black layer indicates presence of graphene (see text above).

Protocol for collecting samples from graphene (100%) sprays: following Figure 8, remove the lid (1) and bring the can nozzle close to a sterile glass vial (2), then press the trigger lever to activate the pump and fill the sterile vial with a sufficient volume of the product (3), finally pipette the product from the glass vial to prepare the testing concentrations.

Figure 8: Steps to be performed on the graphene (100%) sprays prior to cell culture testing. Third picture represents sample on a test vial prior to cell exposure, black dots indicate presence of graphene (see text above).

2.4 UC4: Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) in Polymer Foils for thermal Applications

UC4 deals with polyurethane based film materials for surface heaters, e.g. in a car seat. The polyurethane is filled up to 6 wt.-% with multi-walled carbon nanotubes (CNT). For end-of-life scenarios of the composite materials (1) incineration and (2) shredding was taken into account. Due to the complex manufacturing process of the CNT filled PU foils, the handling and packing of the material and its powder additional contamination with bacteria/fungi and/or endotoxin cannot be excluded.

(1) Sample collection for end-of-life scenario incineration: The sample collection for incineration analysis is simple. Since the CNT filled PU foils are available as a roll good on release paper (Figure 9), appropriate sample pieces can be assembled by cutting. Afterwards the foil is delaminated from the release paper and can directly be used for incineration analysis without further preparation.

Figure 9: CNT filled PU foils as a roll good on release paper.

(2) Sample collection for end-of-life scenario shredding: For the end-of-life scenario shredding an adapted process for the sample collection was used. As an approach, milling in an ultra-centrifugal mill was carried out. As described above for the incineration sample collection, a piece of CNT filled PU foil (approx. 22 g) was cut from a roll and the foil was delaminated from the release paper. The milling was performed in a two-step process: At first milling was done with 10,000 rpm for 1 min by using a 2 mm sieve (Figure 10a). In a second step, a 1 mm sieve was used to reduce the particle size to values ≤ 1 mm (Figure 10b). The resulting powders were collected (Figure 10c) and provided to the partners in the MACRAMÉ consortium.

Figure 10: Milling was performed in an ultra-centrifugal mill. In a first step (a) a 2 mm sieve was used for milling with 10,000 rpm for 1 min. In a second step (b) a 1 mm sieve was used for milling with 10,000 rpm for 1 min. The samples (c) were collected afterwards.

2.5 UC5: Poly lactic-co-glycolic acid (PLGA) for inhalable antibiotics (Material Family: PLCG)

This UC basically provides ciprofloxacin loaded PLGA nanoparticles for inhalation therapy, produced by My BioTech under GMP-like conditions. In parallel, especially fluorescence or gold-labelled PLGA particles are provided to test and further develop MACRAMÉ's methodologies such as laser ablation inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (LA-ICP-MS) and Time-of-Flight Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry (ToF-SIMS). The combination of different particles is used to explore methods for the description of cellular uptake and to describe the uptake of MyBioTech particles in single cell models (alveolar macrophages) and more complex 3d cell culture and/or ex vivo models with lung-like architecture. Samples are provided as aliquots in liquid form following a production process performed under Good Laboratory Practice (GLP) conditions as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Process leading to sampling of MyBiotech particles.

Protocol for collecting samples from Ciprofloxacin loaded PCL NPs: the material is harvested using a 3-way valve to direct the sample flow to the collection container, run the process till desired batch size (volume) is collected. Use the three-way valve to direct the flow to waste line, close the lid of the container and stop the process (Figure 12, Table 2).

Figure 12: Samples to be shipped for further assessment are enumerated in Table 2.

These particles are also prepared for additional physico-chemical characterization method development where they are modified with Lumogen Red F 305 fluorescent dye (commercially available from BASF) absorption (red) or loaded with Au NPs of size 15nm and 50nm. The list of samples prepared is provided in Table 2.

Table 2: Samples already shipped to MACRAMÉ partners for further characterisation. The first four items are shown in Figure 12.

Blank PCL LNC
Cipro Loaded PCL NPs
Lumogen Labelled PCL NPs
Cipro Loaded Lumogen Labelled PCL NPs
Au NP (15nm) loaded PCL NPs
Au NP (50nm) loaded PCL NPs

3 Conclusions

This deliverable reports the processes developed by MACRAMÉ industrial partners to collect both pristine and processed samples prior to sending them to MACRAMÉ experimental partners. Most samples are solid, and all are stable and do not require special transport conditions regarding timelines and temperatures and will be used for further (eco)toxicity testing by *WP2 - Development and Advancement of Characterisation- & Test-Methods &-Protocols* and *WP4 - Definition, Demonstration & Validation of MACRAMÉ Methods in Use-Cases* partners. Further SOPs developed by *WP2 - Development and Advancement of Characterisation- & Test-Methods &-Protocols* partners regarding adaptation of industrial samples to the particular conditions necessary for further laboratory work and *in vitro* testing with cells will be reported under MACRAMÉ *Deliverable D2.2: Report on the SOPs developed by WP2*.